

Leadership Communication in Increasing Employee Work Productivity

Andi Muh Rusdi Maidin

Department of Sociology, Makassar University Bosowa, Makassar, South Sulawesi, Indonesia

Rajamemang

Department of Public Administration, Sinjai University Muhammadiyah, Sinjai Utara, South Sulawesi, Indonesia

Wahyudi Putera

Study Program Accounting, STIE Pelita Buana Makassar, South Sulawesi, Indonesia

Muhammad Sabir Maidin

Faculty Comparative Schools of Thought and Law, Alauddin State Islamic University, South Sulawesi, Indonesia

Saripuddin

Graduate School, Economic Education, Patempo University, South Sulawesi, Indonesia

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Abstract:

This study aims to determine the communication of leaders to subordinates in improving employee productivity at the Kajuru Sub-District Office. The research methodology uses qualitative type, observation data collection techniques, interviews and documentation. Data analysis techniques data reduction, data presentation and conclusion drawing. The results of research on the communication of leaders to subordinates in improving employee productivity at the Kajuru Sub-District Office have been carried out optimally, both downward communication and upward communication. The downward communication carried out by the

Kajuru Sub-District Head has been carried out optimally, especially in terms of instructions or tasks, rational, ideology, information, and feedback. Likewise, the upward communication at the Kajuru Sub-District Office has been maximized, this is evidenced by the tenure of the State Civil Apparatus (ASN) of the Kajuru Sub-District Office, where the average employee tenure is approximately 15 years, of course the employees have experience and understand their duties and functions at the Kajuru Sub-District Office and of course the communication that has been established is very close between superiors and subordinates. The output of this research is in the form of articles published both in print and electronic form, so that the community, especially students, can access easily and at a low cost. The goal is that students can read and know the author's findings regarding the communication of leaders to subordinates in increasing employee productivity at the Kajuru Sub-District Office.

Keywords: *Communication, Work Productivity.*

Introduction

The State Civil Apparatus has an important meaning in improving the bureaucratic system towards an organizational posture and human

resource profile that is more efficient, effective, accountable and competent. The development of the civil apparatus towards an independent and professional nature continues to be carried

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out, one of which is with the existence of Law No. 5 of 2014 concerning the State Civil Apparatus (ASN). As an organization, the bureaucracy is not only focused on pursuing the achievement of maximum work productivity, but also paying more attention to performance in the process of achievement. Thus communication is one of the key factors for every State Civil Apparatus and organization in achieving work productivity.

In a government or private agency, good communication is needed to realize work productivity in achieving predetermined goals. Work productivity is a result of work requirements that must be met by employees to obtain maximum results where in its implementation, work productivity lies in the

human factor as the implementer of work activities. So the human factor plays an important role in achieving results in accordance with the objectives of the agency, because no matter how perfect the work equipment without human labor will not succeed in producing goods or services in accordance with the objectives to be achieved (Baik, 2021).

Work productivity essentially includes an attitude that always has the view that today's work methods must be better than yesterday's work methods, and the results that can be achieved tomorrow must be more or more qualified than the results achieved today (Michie, 2023) Work productivity is often defined as the ability of a person or group of people to produce maximum quality work.

Table 1. Recapitulation of Employee Performance Appraisal at the Kajuara Sub-District Office 2020 – 2024

Employee Achievement Score	Performance	Year (Person)					Total Assessment Score
		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	
86 – 100 (A) Excellent		8	7	10	12	15	52
76 – 85 (B) Good		15	14	14	10	12	65
66 – 75 (C) Fair		5	5	2	4	3	19
56 – 65 (D) Poor		-	-	-	-	-	-
0 – 55 (E) Very Poor		-	-	-	-	-	-
Total Karyawan		28	26	26	26	30	

Source: Data Processed by Kajuara Sub-District Office, 2024

From the table above, the calculation of the recapitulation of individual employee performance at the Kajuaran Sub-District Office, Bone Regency, it can be seen that the highest score for employee performance assessment is at value B (good) with a total assessment score of 65, then value A (very good) with a total assessment score of 52 and value C (sufficient) with a total assessment score of 19. This certainly shows that there are shortcomings in employee performance at the Kajuaran Sub-District Office, Bone Regency, which should be expected to get category A (very good).

To get a good and high quality work result, good communication is needed. Communication is the delivery of information and understanding

and by using the same signs. Communication is a process used by humans to find common ground through transitions with symbolic messages (Hargie, 2021).

According to Buchholz and Knorre (2023) communication is a process of delivering messages or news carried out by someone and the receipt of the news by another person or small group of people with an immediate effect and feedback. Good communication relations between superiors and subordinates, subordinates and superiors, and between subordinates and subordinates in an organization are very influential in bridging the creation of increased employee productivity in the organization.

To carry out work smoothly and avoid misunderstandings in order to achieve common goals that are agreed upon and set, leaders at various levels and staff must create elements of good cooperation. With the process of cooperation, the element of communication will automatically be created in an organization. Because any form of instructions, information, reviews, input, reports from leaders to subordinates and vice versa are always carried out through the communication process (Bucchi and Trench, 2021).

A good relationship between leaders and subordinates cannot be separated from a good communication in influencing company performance (job performance) so as to achieve good performance results. The tendency of leaders to prioritize communication skills will be greater knowing the inherent obscurity in the organization. The existence of talks with its members will build an environment and understand new situations that require the acquisition of shared information. The emotional approach taken by the leadership provides its own impetus for employees in an effort to improve work performance as desired, namely the creation of a harmonious relationship for the leaders (Jamaludin, 2021).

The above phenomenon requires a leadership that can place itself according to the character of the people it faces. The ability of a leader like this will make it easier for him to determine what messages to convey that can provide his own motives for growing work enthusiasm for the progress of employee performance so that communication goals can be realized as expected by the leadership.

Some studies that link communication and work productivity include Working through databases has become an integral and important part of work in business. The availability of knowledge and information from any location contributes to better networking and greater transparency in the company and enables collaborative working regardless of location. The relationship between informal communication through four communication channels and a) the efficiency of work through databases and b) their need for

quality of work was investigated (Stöckl and Struck, 2022). Then the need for effective delivery in language has always been emphasized among speakers. Accurate and concise information transfer processes have been shown to be closely related to performance and progress in any field. Studies that provide an overview of how communication affects productivity in completing tasks on time. An online survey was conducted through social media of construction site supervisors across Malaysia to get their feedback regarding the medium used to communicate with their fellow workers and the importance of English for communication in the construction industry (Ne'Matullah, et al, 2021). Research that aims 1) Knowing the effect of work communication on employee productivity. 2) Knowing the effect of work discipline on employee work productivity. 3) Knowing the effect of compensation on employee work productivity. 4) Knowing the effect of the work environment on employee productivity (Askiah, et al, 2022). And this study is to determine the effect of compensation, communication, and work discipline on employee productivity. This research was conducted at companies engaged in manufacturing and construction, especially paving, concrete, buildings and housing (Aprilia, et al, 2023).

Theory Review

Communication

According to Chitode (2021) in business communications: Theory translated by, "Communication is a process of exchanging information between individuals through a common system, either by symbols, signals, or behavior or actions".

Craig and Xiong (2022), define communication as:

- a. The spread (transmission, delivery, passing) of energy changes from one place to another, as in nerve transmission.
- b. The process of transmitting or receiving signs, signals or messages;

c. One message or signal;

Furthermore, Craig and Xiong (2022), revealed that communication is the flow of information and emotions contained in society that takes place vertically (up and down) and horizontally. It can also mean the connection or connection of vehicles / means. Communication is the capacity of individuals or groups to convey feelings, thoughts and desires to other individuals and groups. What needs to be considered in communication is communication techniques.

There are three components that must be present in the communicator, namely:

- a. Source credibility refers to the extent to which the source is seen as having expertise and is trusted. The more expert and trusted the source of information, the more effective the message delivered.
- b. The attractiveness of a communicator can occur due to physical appearance, speaking style, personal traits, familiarity, performance, communication skills and behavior.
- c. The source is favored by the community may be because the source has something in common in terms of needs, expectations and feelings.

Communication is the basis for cooperation, if done well, it will help the company achieve its goals. To achieve the goals of the company, effective communication is needed as a process of interaction or relationship with each other that is desired to be accepted and understood between superiors and subordinates and with their superiors.

Work Productivity

Productivity according to the National Productivity Council has the meaning of a mental attitude that always views that the quality of life must be better than yesterday and tomorrow must be better than today. The International Labor Organization in Citaristi (2022), reveals that in a simpler way the meaning of productivity is a comparison in arithmetic between the amount produced and the amount of each source used during production. These

sources can be land, raw and auxiliary materials, factories, machines, and tools, human labor.

Ariani, et al (2023). Said that: "Productivity is a comparison between the results of work in the form of goods or services with the sources or energy used in a production process. In general, productivity can be interpreted as a comparison between output and input and expresses how to utilize both sources in producing a good or service.

According to Sinungan, what is meant by work productivity can be grouped into three, namely:

- a. The traditional formulation for overall productivity is nothing but the ratio of what is produced to the overall production equipment used.
- b. Productivity is basically a mental attitude that always has the view that the quality of life today must be better than yesterday, and tomorrow must be better than today.
- c. Productivity is a harmoniously integrated interaction of three essential factors, namely: investment including the use of knowledge and technology and management research and labor.

Conceptual Framework

In the qualitative descriptive analysis in this study, it will be described how the form of leadership communication in improving employee work productivity at the kajuara sub-district office. The concept of the conceptual framework above can be realized in the following chart:

Figure 1. Schematic Conceptual Framework
Source: Jackson and Mazzei, 2022

Research Method

The type of research used is descriptive qualitative research (Savin-Baden and Major, 2023) describes that qualitative methods are research that intends to understand the phenomenon of what is experienced by research subjects, for example, behavior, perception, motivation, action and others. Qualitative methods are used because of several considerations. First, problem solving will be easier when dealing with multiple realities. Second, this method uses directly the nature of the relationship between researchers and respondents. Third, this method is more sensitive and more adaptable to the patterns encountered (Jackson and Mazzei, 2022). This researcher took the location in Kajuara District, Bone Regency.

Data collection techniques are observation, interviews and documentation. Data analysis techniques in this qualitative research with data reduction which includes the process of summarizing and sorting data related to the main things focusing on important things, presenting data which can be interpreted as organizing data that has been educated and based on the organized data, the researcher provides interpretation and then draws conclusions about the patterns of regularity or deviation that exist in the phenomenon under study (Savin-Baden and Major, 2023).

Discussion

Forms of Leadership Communication in Improving Employee Work Productivity at the Kajuara Sub-District Office

Communication is very important in doing a job especially in the scope of government. Communication between leaders and subordinates greatly affects the increase in employee productivity, if there is poor communication between leaders to subordinates, subordinates with subordinates, the increase in work productivity will decrease. For this reason, communication is needed so that the goals to be achieved in the organization can be realized properly. The form of

communication consists of two forms, namely the upward communication form and the downward communication form.

Downward Communication

Downward communication is communication conveyed from superiors to subordinates. The use of this communication is very effective for delivering instructions, direction, control to subordinates. Downward communication needs to be done as a form of effort to implement policies, work procedures, and regulations that exist in the agency. The types of downward communication applied to the Kajuara Sub-District Head Office are:

1. Instruction or task

Instructions or tasks are directions or orders given by leaders to subordinates to do something. Instructions are useful for clarifying what is expected and how the process works. When conveying messages or information to subordinates, leaders must communicate in accordance with what is expected in an agency so that the communication messages conveyed can be understood properly by subordinates.

Based on the results of interviews conducted by researchers with the Head of the Kajuara Sub-District Head Office in giving instructions to subordinates, he stated that:

"In giving instructions, as a leader, I prefer to meet directly with subordinates, for example related to activity programs (implementation, obstacles, achievement of program objectives). There are things that I want to coordinate, I meet directly with the relevant field. If there are things that want to be coordinated with the head of the field, I as the leader will meet directly and give instructions by using good communication so that the main tasks and scope of his authority run well". (Interview Result, 13/04/2024)

Based on the results of observations, interviews and documentation, it can be concluded that the instructions given by the Head of the Kajuara Sub-District Head Office to subordinates are by using direct communication where the head of the sub-district holds meetings with related fields to discuss program issues in accordance with the

field of work of subordinates, with direct communication.

With direct communication, of course, the instructions conveyed run well in accordance with the main tasks and scope of their authority. In line with the research results A clear relationship was revealed between informal communication and work effectiveness through the database as well as their need for quality work. The extent of this relationship, however, varies depending on the type and purpose of informal communication. This research highlights the necessity of informal communication for digital collaborative work and therefore has significant implications for the quality of work.

2. Rational

Rational is the provision of instructions by the leader regarding the reason or purpose of a task that needs to be done, good communication is very important for agencies so that employees can pursue the tasks they are doing related to organizational objectivity. The purpose of rational messages is to increase the motivation and passion of employees by providing direction regarding the importance of a task or job.

Based on the results of interviews conducted by researchers with the Head of the Kajuaru Sub-District Head Office, he said that:

"As a leader, I try to motivate my employees, work motivation is important because if work motivation is higher, employee work productivity will also be higher". (Interview Results, 13/04/2024)

The provision of motivation carried out by leaders to their subordinates aims to encourage growth in a person both from within and outside to do a job with high enthusiasm using the abilities and skills they have.

Based on the results of observations, interviews, and documentation, it can be concluded that the head of the sub-district has carried out rational downward communication to subordinates, giving instructions by the leadership regarding the reasons or objectives of a task that needs to be done, the head of the sub-district always emphasizes that employees can develop a career

or to achieve a higher career level it must be accompanied by work motivation, and this has been done as evidenced by the average education of Kajuaru Sub-district Office employees who have a bachelor's degree. In line with the research results show that language barriers have affected workers' productivity. The lack of effective delivery of information and instructions causes delays in project implementation in the construction sector in Malaysia (Ne'Matullah, et al, 2021).

3. Ideology

Ideology, namely the leader gives a rational message whose emphasis is on explaining the task and its relation to the vision and mission of the organization including strengthening employee loyalty.

Based on the results of interviews conducted by researchers with the Head of the Kajuaru Sub-District Head Office explained that:

"Ideology is actually very important to be conveyed to every employee in this office because this is related to the progress of the Kajuaru District Office, if employees do not know what the achievements of this office are vision and mission, it is impossible for them to work according to what we want". (Interview Result, 13/04/2024).

With the delivery of ideological messages related to the goals that each agency wants to achieve through the tasks carried out by the staff. Conveying messages about the goals to be achieved is intended so that employees understand the vision and mission of the office. In realizing this, the leader maintains a good communication relationship or competence so that the assigned tasks run well and improve work performance, so that the level of employee work productivity is getting better. In line with the results of the study found that 1) Shows that the influence of work communication variables on work productivity has a positive and significant relationship. 2) Shows that the influence of work discipline variables on work productivity has a positive and significant relationship. 3) Indicates that the influence of compensation variables on work productivity

has a positive and significant relationship. 4) Indicates that the influence of work environment variables on work productivity has a positive and significant relationship (Askiah, et al, 2022).

4. Information

Conveying information about policies in the agency. This policy is used to regulate the performance of employees of an agency in controlling behavior so as not to deviate so as not to harm the agency.

Based on the results of interviews conducted by researchers with the Head of the Kajuara District Head Office, he said that:

"I inform all employees here because it is very important so that employees want to work according to their respective tasks and duties, in accordance with existing procedures". (Interview Result, 13/04/2024)

Information messages are intended to introduce subordinates to the rules, benefits, and habits contained in the agency. It is intended that every employee in the agency can carry out their duties in accordance with existing procedures.

Based on the results of interviews conducted by researchers, it can be concluded that information in downward communication by leaders in the Kajuara Sub-District Head Office in order to create a good communication relationship between leaders and subordinates and also to increase employee work productivity through a Decree (SK) issued by the Kajuara Sub-District Head of Bone Regency. In line with the research results, it was found that compensation has a positive and significant effect on employee work productivity. Communication has a positive and significant effect on employee work productivity. Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on employee work productivity. Good compensation is believed to encourage employees to want to work more productively. Good communication will increase employee productivity. Paying attention to employee discipline is very necessary because if employees are disciplined at work, employees can be said to be productive (Aprilia, et al, 2023).

5. Feedback

Feedback is a message that contains information about the accuracy of individual information in doing their work. One simple form of this feedback is the provision of a reward in the form of a salary that is ready to do his job or if there is no information from the leadership criticizing his work, it means that his work is satisfactory. But if the employee's work is not good, the feedback may be in the form of criticism or warning to the employee.

Based on the results of research through observation, it was found that if there was indiscipline in the work of employees, sanctions were given in the form of giving a Warning Letter (SP), while for employee salary data, when the researcher asked about this, the informant replied that the salary data of the Kajuara Sub-District Office employees was a secret of the sub-district government so that it could not be published.

Based on the results of interviews conducted by researchers with the Head of the Kajuara Sub-District Head Office, he said that:

"Government services at the Sub-District Office are not as smooth as words, there are also problems but thank God it can be covered well, so that it does not affect employee performance". (Interview Results, 13/04/2024)

The results of an interview with the Secretary of Kajuara Sub-District said that:

"The sub-district head always emphasizes to employees that all are entitled to rights and have the right to convey their aspirations in order to create unity in carrying out their duties properly". (Interview Result, 15/04/2024)

Based on the results of interviews conducted by researchers, it is known that feedback has been maximized, although in this study there is no supporting data related to employee salaries, but from the information obtained that employee salaries have been paid according to their class.

The overall research results related to downward communication between the sub-district head and his subordinates starting from instructions, rational, ideology, information, and feedback

have run optimally. The instructions given by the sub-district head to subordinates are by using direct communication. Rational communication has been carried out through giving instructions according to the reason or purpose of the task needs to be done, such as emphasizing that employees can develop their careers and this has been done as evidenced by the average education of Kajuaru Sub-District Office employees who have a bachelor's degree. Ideological communication has also been implemented. Likewise, information communication has been carried out, and also communication through feedback has been carried out optimally in the Kajuaru Sub-District Office.

Upward Communication

Upward communication is communication with the flow of messages flowing from subordinates or lower levels to higher levels. Opening upward communication channels is very important to find out the attitudes or complaints experienced by subordinates towards agencies or organizations.

Based on the results of research through observation at the Kajuaru Sub-District Office, data were obtained on the length of service of each State Civil Apparatus (ASN) at the Kajuaru Sub-District Office, while data related to Employee Performance Reports, when researchers asked about this, the Informant replied that the Employee Performance Report was a secret of the sub-district government so that it could not be published.

Based on the results of interviews conducted by researchers with the Head of the Kajuaru Sub-District Head Office, he said that:

"We still maintain upward communication from below, because by implementing this we can find out what obstacles are faced by subordinates, because the purpose of communication is to provide feedback such as suggestions and directions". (Interview Results, 15/04/2024)

Furthermore, an interview with the Secretary of Kajuaru Sub-District said that:

"Actually, we as subordinates always convey information related to our respective work, how our next target is and convey the ideas we have

to the leadership, we also always ask for solutions if obstacles occur. In conveying it, we also use body language because I think it is important so that it is not flat". (Interview Results, 15/08/2024)

Based on the results of the author's interview, it can be concluded that upward communication at the Kajuaru Sub-District Office has been maximized, this is evidenced by the tenure of the State Civil Apparatus (ASN) of the Kajuaru Sub-District Office, where the average employee tenure is approximately 15 years, of course the employees have experience and understand their duties and functions at the Kajuaru Sub-District Office and of course the communication that exists is very close between superiors and subordinates.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, it shows that the communication of leaders to subordinates in improving employee productivity at the Kajuaru Sub-District Office has been carried out optimally, both downward communication and upward communication.

Communication downward between the sub-district head and his subordinates starting from instructions, rational, ideology, information, and feedback has been running optimally. The instructions given by the sub-district head to subordinates are by using direct communication. Rational communication has been carried out through giving instructions according to the reason or purpose of the task needs to be done, such as emphasizing that employees develop their careers and this has been done as evidenced by the average education of Kajuaru Sub-District Office employees who have a bachelor's degree. Ideology communication has also been implemented. Likewise, information communication has been carried out, and also communication through feedback has been maximally carried out at the Kajuaru Sub-District Office.

Communication upwards at the Kajuaru Sub-District Office has been maximized, this is evidenced by the tenure of the Kajuaru Sub-

District Office State Civil Apparatus (ASN), where the average employee tenure is approximately 15 years which of course the employees have experience and understand their duties and functions at the Kajua Sub-District Office and of course the communication that has been established is very close between superiors and subordinates.

References

- Ariani, R., Hardhienata, S., & Entang, M. (2023). Increasing work productivity through organizational culture, visionary leadership, and achievement motivation. *SUJANA: Education and Learning Review*, 39-52.
- Askiah, A., Fauziah, F., Rahmasita, A. N., & Sabtohadji, J. (2022). Influence of communication, discipline, compensation and work environment on employee work productivity at pt. steel facilities studies in the city of Samarinda. *Jurnal Scientia*, 11(02), 516-521.
- Aprilia, R., Turmudhi, A., Purwasih, R., Maimunah, S., & Yunggoli, S. (2023, August). Work Productivity: Compensation, Communication and Work Discipline. In *International Conference on Intelligent Networking and Collaborative Systems* (pp. 349-360). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Buchholz, U., & Knorre, S. (2023). *Internal communication and management*. Springer Books.
- Balk, B. M. (2021). *Productivity*. Springer International Publishing.
- Bucchi, M., & Trench, B. (Eds.). (2021). *Routledge handbook of public communication of science and technology*. Routledge.
- Chitode, J. S. (2021). *Communication theory*. Technical Publications.
- Craig, R. T., & Xiong, B. (2022). Traditions of communication theory and the potential for multicultural dialogue. *Journal of Multicultural Discourses*, 17(1), 1-25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17447143.2021.2009487>
- Citaristi, I. (2022). International Labour Organization—ILO. In *The Europa Directory of International Organizations 2022* (pp. 343-349). Routledge.
- Hargie, O. (2021). *Skilled interpersonal communication: Research, theory and practice*. Routledge.
- Indonesia, P. N. R. (2014). Undang-Undang Nomor 5 Tahun 2014 tentang Aparatur Sipil Negara.
- Iriani, N., Rahman, A., Muchtar, A., Putera, W., & Maidin, A. M. R. (2023). Cara Meningkatkan Kinerja Guru Dalam Pengalaman Mengajar, Kompetensi Guru, dan Budaya Kerja Pada SMA Negeri 9 Kabupaten Bulukumba. *Jurnal Ilmiah Ecosystem*, 23(2). <https://doi.org/10.35965/eco.v23i2.2839>
- Iriani, N., Rosnaeni, R., Arjang, A., & Putera, W. (2024). The Impact of Leadership, Work Culture and Motivation Region of District Legislature Employees. *The Management Journal of Binaniaga*, 9(01), 15-34. <http://dx.doi.org/10.33062/mjb.v9i01.59>
- Iriani, N., Agustianti, A., Suciанти, R., Rahman, A., & Putera, W. (2024). Understanding Risk and Uncertainty Management: A Qualitative Inquiry into Developing Business Strategies Amidst Global Economic Shifts, Government Policies, and Market Volatility. *Golden Ratio of Finance Management*, 4(2), 62-77. <https://doi.org/10.52970/grfm.v4i2.444>
- Jamaludin, M. (2021). The influence of supply chain management on competitive advantage and company performance. *Uncertain Supply Chain Management*, 9(3), 696-704. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5267/j.uscm.2021.4.009>
- Jackson, A. Y., & Mazzei, L. A. (2022). *Thinking with theory in qualitative research*. Routledge.
- Michie, J. (2023). Productivity, Innovation and Sustainability. In *Prospects and Policies for Global Sustainable Recovery: Promoting Environmental and Economic Sustainability* (pp. 173-214). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Maidin, R., Nurdin, M., Putera, W., Aliza, N., Qalsum, A. T. U., & Yahya, I. L. (2022). Implementation of the Targeted Electricity Subsidy Policy at the Office of PT. PLN (Persero) ULP Sinjai. *International Journal of Public*

Administration and Management Research, 8(3), 29-41.

Maidin, A. M. R., Putera, W., Sabir, M., & Ulmi, A. T. (2023). Cigarettes, Betel Leaves, and Areca Nuts in the Activities of the Tolotang Community of Benteng Indonesia. *Revista de Gestão Social e Ambiental*, 17(7), e03657-e03657. <https://doi.org/10.24857/rgsa.v17n7-021>

Maidin, A. M., Bahri, S., Putera, W., & Rasyid, A. (2023). Puskesmas Strategy in Improving the Performance of Posyandu Cadres. *THE American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (THE AJHSSR)*, 6(6), 35-47. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.56805/ajhssr>

Maidin, A. M. R., Arifin, D. P., Tenri Ulmi Qalsum, A., & Yahya, I. L. (2022). Determinants of Attractiveness of the Sacred Area of Pakkwarue Wells. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research*, 6(1.2). <http://dx.doi.org/10.29099/ijair.v6i1.2.798>

Maidin, A. M. R., & Putera, W. (2023). Organizational Communication Ethics in Supporting Service Quality in Government. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology (IJISRT)*, 8(11), 1796-1809. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10275660>

Maidin, A. M. R., Putera, W., Baharuddin, H. A., & Qalsum, A. T. U. (2023). The Role of Social Interaction in Developing Mosque Activities. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*,

1(4), 894-900. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(4\).84](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(4).84)

Ne'Matullah, K. F., Roslan, S. A., & Lim, S. P. (2021). Impact of communication on work productivity in construction industry. *St. Theresa Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 7(1), 38-53.

Rajamemang, A. M., Nurdin, M., Putera, W., & Wahyuti, A. T. Effectiveness of Licensing Services for Issuing Business Identification Numbers Through the Oss-Rba System at the Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office of Sinjai Regency. *The American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (THE AJHSSR)*, 6(2), 63-70, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.56805/ajhssr>

Savin-Baden, M., & Major, C. (2023). *Qualitative research: The essential guide to theory and practice*. Routledge.

Stöckl, A., & Struck, O. (2022). The impact of informal communication on the quality and productivity of digital collaborative work. *Work*, 72(4), 1655-1671. <https://doi.org/10.3233/wor-211246>

Saripuddin., Kadir, D., Putera, W., & Yahya, I. L. (2022). Government Policy Through Market Orientation in Supporting the Business Performance of Maros Bread Business in Maros Regency. *International journal of capacity building in education and management*, 5(2), 1-21. <http://dx.doi.org/10.36758/ijcbem>